

COAR NARRATIVE SERIES

The role of repositories in maintaining research integrity

Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR)

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Pressure on the scholarly record

Science is built on a foundation of trust. Researchers, institutions, publishers, and the public all rely on the assumption that published findings represent honest, rigorous, and transparent inquiry. Yet, that foundation is under increasing strain. Across disciplines and institutions worldwide, problems of research integrity are growing in scale and complexity, raising questions about the reliability of the scientific record and the credibility of the enterprise itself.

The most egregious violations of research integrity are fabrications and falsifications, which typically involve inventing or manipulating data to support a desired conclusion (Rubin, 2022). While such cases have historically been considered to be quite rare (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2017), their consequences can be severe. In medicine and public health, falsified findings have led to harmful treatments, misallocated resources, and lasting damage to public trust (Mousavi & Abdollahi, 2020; Motta & Stecula, 2021). Beyond the damage caused by these more isolated cases, a growing industry has emerged around the production of fake papers. Paper mills – operations that sell researchers completely fabricated manuscripts – now represent a systemic threat to the scholarly record (Parker et al., 2024; Richardson et al., 2025). Indeed, in some open datasets, mass-manufactured articles were estimated to outnumber legitimate research papers by as much as ten to one (Barnett & Spick, 2026).

Traditional publishers are reportedly being swamped by fraudulent papers as the widespread availability of AI tools accelerates this trend, and are now spending significant resources on trying to screen out these papers (Chawla, 2025), but they are still often passing undetected through editorial control (Bik, 2026). The emergence of agentic AI (MIT Sloan School of Management, 2026) – systems capable of generating complete manuscripts without a human-driven research question – is further straining the resources available to publishers and platforms to filter out such work.

Deliberate fraud, however, is not the only threat to the integrity of the scientific record. Even research conducted in good faith can undermine confidence in science when its findings cannot be independently reproduced – a pattern now widely referred to as the “replication crisis” (Caffrey, 2024). A landmark effort in 2015 by the Open Science Collaboration, for example, attempted to replicate 100 published psychology studies and found that fewer than half produced results consistent with the original findings. Since then, similar concerns have emerged across medicine (Errington et al., 2021) or economics (Camerer et al., 2016). The growing use of AI and machine learning in the research process introduces additional complexity: as noted in the Royal Society Report on Science in the Age of AI (2024), reproducing AI-based research requires not only replicating the methods, code, data, and the environmental conditions under which the experiment was conducted,

but also transparency about the training data used to develop the tool, which can also unintentionally introduce biases into findings.

The problem may also be self-reinforcing, as AI increases the speed at which low-quality and fabricated material enters the scholarly record. Because large language models are continuously retrained on new content, fabrications risk being absorbed and amplified with each cycle (COAR, 2026). Over time, the boundary between genuine and fabricated knowledge risks becoming increasingly difficult to detect, not only for the public but for researchers themselves.

Averting a crisis

Increasingly, the same technologies that enable fraud are also being deployed in its defence (Candal-Pedreira & Ruano-Ravina, 2026). AI tools are now capable of screening millions of papers for textual signatures associated with paper mill activity (Cabanac et al., 2022), flagging image manipulation with a precision that outpaces human review (Chaturvedi et al., 2025), and identifying statistical inconsistencies (Nuijten & Polanin, 2020) that might otherwise pass unnoticed through peer review. But AI-assisted detection can only go so far. Fraud and its detection are engaged in a continuous arms race, and a system that depends primarily on catching misconduct after the fact will always be playing catch-up.

A more durable response lies upstream, across three reinforcing dimensions: incentive structures that reward rigour over quantity, open science practices that make the research process transparent and verifiable, and infrastructure that preserves provenance and supports accountability over time.

The incentive dimension

The open science practices that are needed to strengthen research integrity will only become the norm when the scholarly community changes the way researchers are evaluated. The prevailing "publish or perish" culture remains one of the most significant structural drivers of integrity problems. By rewarding quantity over quality, researchers are incentivised to maximise output at the expense of rigour (Edwards & Roy, 2017). When career advancement depends on publication counts, researchers engage in "salami slicing", dividing a single study into multiple smaller papers to maximise outputs. And when the journals favour positive findings, null and negative results go unpublished, creating a systematic bias in the evidence base that others then build upon. An international survey of more than 3,000 researchers across 45 countries found that most researchers were knowledgeable about open research practices, pointing rather to an incentive problem than to one of awareness (Pennington et al., 2026). The study found that the limited uptake of open science was due to incentive structures, funding, and the need for recognition.

Until these incentives change, researchers will continue to prioritise publishable results over robust and transparent research practices.

Significant efforts to reform research assessment are already underway, most notably in Europe. The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA), launched in 2022, has brought together hundreds of universities, funders, and research organisations committed to moving assessment systems away from reductive bibliometric indicators and toward qualitative, multidimensional evaluation. With growing governmental and institutional support, CoARA represents one of the most significant structural interventions currently in motion. Other countries, such as China, are also changing how they evaluate research. China has been shifting away from the decades-long reliance on quantitative metrics toward a more diverse set of measures that emphasise quality, innovation, and societal impact (Shu et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2026). As more countries follow suit, such as the Netherlands (Rushforth 2025), the United Kingdom (Research on Research Institute, n.d.), and others, there is reason to expect a gradual but meaningful transition in publication practices across the research community in the coming years, although the impact will ultimately depend on how fully and consistently its principles are adopted in practice by governments and universities.

Open science as a structural response

In combination with research assessment reform, open science is the most effective approach for addressing integrity challenges because it allows for greater scrutiny of the data, code, and methodologies underlying published findings. In this sense, transparency is more than a vague scientific principle but a very practical mechanism for creating a trustworthy scholarly communications ecosystem. When research outputs are openly available, errors and inconsistencies are more likely to be identified and flagged by the broader community. Replication becomes possible in a meaningful sense because the underlying materials are accessible rather than locked away on hard drives and available only on request. This openness also creates a durable record: datasets, code, and preprints published in repositories persist beyond the lifespan of any individual project or institution, allowing findings to be revisited, re-analysed, challenged, or built upon over time. While there are some cases of open data being exploited (Spick et al., 2026), this issue can be best addressed through more careful examination of the papers and data rather than a retreat from openness.

Transparency in data, code, and methods addresses one dimension of the integrity challenge, but the processes used to evaluate research also require greater openness. Peer review, which is the cornerstone of quality control in academic publishing, could significantly contribute to strengthening research integrity if it were made openly available. At its most basic level, making the review process visible by publishing the content of reviews and the reviewers' identities creates much greater accountability.

Reviewers who know their assessments will be seen by others may engage more carefully with a manuscript, and be less likely to approve work without proper scrutiny (Walsh et al., 2000). Moreover, publishing review reports alongside articles gives readers a fuller picture of how a paper was evaluated, what concerns were raised, and how authors responded, rather than presenting acceptance as a straightforward and opaque endorsement. The openness of peer reviews may also have a preventive effect: authors who know their work will face visible, attributable critique, may want to ensure that their work can withstand public scrutiny. The emerging Publish, Review, Curate (PRC) model, in which manuscripts are posted as preprints, reviewed openly, and then curated, represents one of the most promising efforts to reconfigure scholarly publishing along these lines. PRC – which is gaining traction across the scholarly community – is an umbrella term for a diverse set of open review approaches.

The evidence that these practices can make a difference is compelling. A cross-disciplinary analysis found that the proportion of papers reporting positive results supporting their tested hypothesis had grown over time, reaching approximately 86% by 2007, with some fields showing even higher rates (Fanelli, 2012). More than a decade later, the pattern persists. A 2021 study comparing conventional and pre-registered psychology research found that 96% of conventional articles reported positive results, compared with only 44% of studies pre-registered through the Registered Reports model (Scheel et al., 2021). This suggests that when the research process is transparent from the outset, the distortions introduced by publication bias and selective reporting are substantially reduced.

Repositories can play a critical role in supporting the integrity of the scholarly record

Research integrity is not just about individual or institutional conduct. It also depends on the infrastructure that holds, links, and provides access to research outputs. When these functions are absent or fragmented, the record itself becomes unreliable, regardless of how rigorously the individual studies were conducted. Repositories play an increasingly important role in this context. They combine the structural elements that are needed to maintain the integrity of the scholarly record over time: provenance metadata, persistent identification, version management, contributor verification, and long-term preservation of resources. In addition, as they are typically affiliated with a university, research institute, or domain community, their governance is more aligned with the research mission rather than with commercial interests. Though researchers still seem to prefer domain-based services or those offered by commercial providers, the advantages of using a repository with institutional backing and community governance will likely become more evident in the current environment.

Provenance and metadata

At the foundation of research integrity lies provenance: the information documenting where a resource came from, how it was created, and how it has changed over time. Structured, detailed metadata, together with persistent access to resources, helps distinguish legitimate scholarship from manufactured or manipulated work. Persistent identifiers ensure that citations remain accessible and trackable even when platforms evolve, close, or change hands. Provenance is further strengthened when related resources are directly linked to each other, as publications to datasets or code to funding sources, enabling others to verify, interpret, and reuse materials with greater confidence. Contributor verification through structured metadata, including ORCID identifiers and CRediT role declarations, also adds granularity to the provenance record by making contributor identities and declared roles more explicit, but there have been examples of misuse of these practices, such as ghost accounts on ORCID (Teixeira da Silva, 2021).

The consequences of inadequate provenance can be profound. A recent preprint by Gibson and colleagues identified two widely used datasets that lacked verifiable provenance and showed signs of fabrication. Despite this, the data had already been used to develop 124 published clinical prediction models, three of which were applied in clinical practice and one was cited in a medical device patent (Gibson et al., 2026). As falsification of scholarly resources becomes more widespread, this kind of structured, machine-readable metadata about provenance becomes an essential safeguard.

Version management

Version control is an essential but often overlooked dimension of good repository management. Research is rarely a static, one-time product: datasets are updated, code is revised, preprints are refined and updated based on feedback, and reports are amended in light of new findings. Without clear versioning information, it becomes impossible for users to know which iteration of a resource they are accessing, whether a more current version exists, and how the content may have changed between iterations. This ambiguity carries real risks. A researcher who cites or builds upon an outdated version of a dataset, an early draft of an article, or a model without realising a more up-to-date version exists could propagate errors through subsequent work. Maintaining clear versioning information also strengthens research integrity more broadly, by creating a transparent audit trail that allows the provenance and evolution of a resource to be traced over time (Klump et al., 2021). This is particularly important in computational research, where the reproducibility of results depends not only on access to data and code but on knowing precisely which version of each was used in a given analysis (Stodden et al., 2016).

Dealing with corrections and retractions

While versioning tracks an author's own revisions to a resource, corrections and retractions reflect its status. However, a broken correction chain poses another risk to scientific integrity. When a publisher retracts an article, the same work may continue to circulate uncorrected in a repository, invisible to readers who have no way of knowing its status has changed. Repositories have not traditionally been proactive in monitoring retractions, though recent developments with Retraction Watch, along with improvements in infrastructure, have made this more tractable. In September 2023, Crossref acquired the Retraction Watch database and by January 2025 had integrated this data into its REST API, enabling systems to query programmatically whether a DOI has been flagged for retraction (Crossref, 2025). This technical advance is complemented at the policy level by the National Information Standards Organisation's (2024) Communication of Retractions, Removals, and Expressions of Concern (CREC) recommended practice, which establishes a standardised framework for how retraction information should flow across platforms. For repositories that hold items with publisher DOIs, regular API queries could enable automated status checking and record updates without manual intervention (Crossref, 2025). Europe PMC's Article Status Monitor demonstrates the feasibility of this approach by accepting publication identifiers in batch and returning status updates – including retractions, withdrawals, and newer versions – surfacing changes that might otherwise pass unnoticed (Rosonovski et al., 2023; Levchenko et al., 2024). As many repositories have not yet considered how to manage retractions, COAR will be convening a working group to develop recommended practices for the management of retractions and corrections in repositories.

Preservation

Provenance, versioning, and correction tracking all depend on the prior condition that the resources themselves remain accessible over time and, as such, digital preservation is a critical prerequisite for research integrity. A scholarly record that cannot be reliably accessed, verified, or built upon over time is one that cannot be trusted – and it is precisely this long-term accessibility and authenticity that digital preservation is designed to guarantee. Repositories are among the most effective institutional responses to this challenge. However, long-term preservation is expensive and requires a full commitment and strategy from the institution at which the repository is based. For this reason, many repositories have adopted only some practices that support preservation, but, to date, have not been able to implement comprehensive preservation strategies. As repositories take on the mantle of digital presentation in support of research integrity, they will need to commit more resources to these activities. Crucially, because most repositories are governed by universities, research institutes, or non-profit organisations, their preservation commitments are not contingent on commercial viability or subject to the

disruptions of acquisition and platform closure that have claimed numerous privately operated scholarly services.

Conclusion

The integrity of science is not a peripheral concern. It is the condition upon which everything else depends: the translation of research into policy, the development of treatments that reach patients, and the public trust that sustains the entire enterprise. The challenges outlined in this piece, from fabrication and falsification to AI-generated papers and irreproducible methods, are not isolated failures of individual researchers acting in bad faith. They are, in large part, the predictable outputs of systems that have rewarded the wrong things for too long.

Repositories sit at the heart of the response to these challenges. As persistent, non-commercial, and community-governed infrastructure, they are uniquely positioned to provide what the current moment demands: structured provenance metadata that makes manipulation harder to conceal, version management that preserves the audit trail of evolving research, correction and retraction signalling that closes the gaps left by publisher-only workflows, and links to open review services that make the evaluation of research visible and accountable. None of these functions is possible without sustained investment and institutional commitment. Yet each is essential.

The path forward requires action on multiple fronts simultaneously: incentive reform, open science practices, and robust infrastructure. Open science enables scrutiny, but only when infrastructure preserves provenance over the long term and incentive systems reward researchers for practising it. Progress in each area strengthens the others, and together they point toward a research ecosystem in which doing science well and being recognised for it are no longer in tension.

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References

- Barnett, A., & Spick, M. (2026, March 17). *Research integrity is locked into an arms race with agentic AI slop*. The London School of Economics and Political Science.
<https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2026/03/17/research-integrity-is-locked-into-an-arms-race-with-agentic-ai-slop/>
- Bik, E. (2026, March 11). *The Camel's camel*. Science Integrity Digest.
<https://scienceintegritydigest.com/2026/03/12/the-camels-camel/>

- Cabanac, G., Labbé, C., & Magazinov, A. (2022). The 'Problematic Paper Screener' automatically selects suspect publications for post-publication (re)assessment. *ArXiv, abs/2210.04895*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2210.04895>
- Caffrey, C. (2024). *Replication crisis*. EBSCO Research Starters. <https://www.ebsco.com/research-starters/science/replication-crisis>
- Candal-Pedreira, C., & Ruano-Ravina, A. (2026). AI for detecting paper mill papers. *BMJ*, 392:s564. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.s564>
- Camerer, C. F., Dreber, A., Forsell, E., Ho, T.-H., Huber, J., Johannesson, M., ... & Wu, H. (2016). Evaluating replicability of laboratory experiments in economics. *Science*, 351(6280), 1433–1436. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaf0918>
- Chaturvedi, A. P., Hibbard, A., Nelson, C., Casadevall, A., & Kullas, A. L. (2025). ASM incorporates Imagetwin to address image duplication and preserve scientific accuracy. *mBio*, 16(10), e0199025. <https://doi.org/10.1128/mbio.01990-25>
- Chawla, D. S. (2025, August 4). *Brokers of scientific fraud growing rapidly, study finds*. Chemical & Engineering News. <https://cen.acs.org/policy/publishing/Brokers-scientific-fraud-growing-rapidly/103/web/2025/08>
- Confederation of Open Access Repositories. (2026, March 3). *Navigating the uneasy interdependence of AI and open science*. <https://coar-repositories.org/news-updates/navigating-the-uneasy-interdependence-of-ai-and-open-science/>
- Crossref. (2025, January 29). *Retraction Watch data in the Crossref REST API*. Crossref Blog. <https://doi.org/10.13003/692016>
- Edwards, M. A., & Roy, S. (2017). Academic research in the 21st century: Maintaining scientific integrity in a climate of perverse incentives and hypercompetition. *Environmental Engineering Science*, 34(1), 51–61. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ees.2016.0223>
- Errington, T. M., Mathur, M., Soderberg, C. K., Denis, A., Perfito, N., Iorns, E., & Nosek, B. A. (2021). Investigating the replicability of preclinical cancer biology. *eLife*, 10, e71601. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.71601>
- Fanelli, D. (2012). Negative results are disappearing from most disciplines and countries. *Scientometrics*, 90(3), 891–904. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-011-0494-7>
- Gibson, A.D., White, N.M., Collins, G.R., & Barnett, A.G. (2026). Evidence of Unreliable Data and Poor Data Provenance in Clinical Prediction Model Research and Clinical Practice. *medRxiv* 26347028. <https://doi.org/10.64898/2026.02.24.26347028>
- Klump, J., Wyborn, L., Wu, M., Martin, J., Downs, R., & Asmi, A. (2021). Versioning data is about more than revisions: A conceptual framework and proposed principles. *Data Science Journal*, 20(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2021-012>
- Levchenko, M., Parkin, M., McEntyre, J., & Harrison, M. (2024). Enabling preprint discovery, evaluation, and analysis with Europe PMC. *PLoS ONE* 19(9): e0303005. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0303005>
- MIT Sloan School of Management. (2026, February 17). *Agentic AI, explained*. <https://mitsloan.mit.edu/ideas-made-to-matter/agentic-ai-explained>
- Motta, M., & Stecula, D. (2021). Quantifying the effect of Wakefield et al. (1998) on skepticism about MMR vaccine safety in the U.S. *PLoS ONE* 16(8): e0256395. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0256395>
- Mousavi, T., & Abdollahi, M. (2020). A review of the current concerns about misconduct in medical sciences publications and the consequences. *DARU Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 28(1), 359–369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40199-020-00332-1>

- National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2017). Addressing research misconduct and detrimental research practices: Current knowledge and issues. In *Fostering Integrity in Research*. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK475962/>
- National Information Standards Organisation. (2024). *NISO RP-45-2024, communication of retractions, removals, and expressions of concern (CREC)*. <https://www.niso.org/publications/rp-45-2024-crec>
- Nuijten, M.B., & Polanin, J.R. (2020). “*statcheck*”: Automatically detect statistical reporting inconsistencies to increase reproducibility of meta-analyses. *Res Syn Meth.* 11: 574–579. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1408>
- Parker, L., Boughton, S., Bero, L., & Byrne, J.A. (2024). Paper mill challenges: past, present, and future. *Methodological aspects of research integrity and culture*, 176, 111549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2024.111549>
- Pennington, C. R., Norris, E., Skubera, M., Ba, Y., Moffat, R., Amaral, O. B., Adamkovi, M., Adgzal, A., Almeida, R. A., Baldwin, J. R., Ballou, N., Behrens, L. M. P., Bertram, M. G., Bjerke, I. E., Blackwell, S. E., Bochynska, A., de Boer, M. R., Buljan, I., Canales-Aguirre, C. B., ... Clark, K. (2026). Awareness and use of open research practices: An international survey of researchers across disciplines. *PsyArXiv* [Preprint]. Retrieved from [osf.io/preprints/psyarxiv/edzxf_v1](https://doi.org/10.1101/2026.01.15.26011111)
- Research on Research Institute. (n.d.). United Kingdom. <https://researchonresearch.org/observatory/united-kingdom/>
- Richardson, R.A.K., Hong, S.S., Byrne, J.A., Stoeger, T. & Amaral, L.A.N. (2025). The entities enabling scientific fraud at scale are large, resilient, and growing rapidly. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 122 (32) e2420092122. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2420092122>
- Rosonovski, S., Levchenko, M., Bhatnagar, R., Chandrasekaran, U., Faulk, L., Hassan, I., Jeffryes, M., Irtaza Mubashar, S., Nassar, M., Jayaprabha Palanisamy, M., Parkin, M., Poluru, J., Rogers, F., Saha, S., Selim, M., Shafique, Z., Ide-Smith, M., Stephenson, D., Tirunagari, S., Venkatesan, A., Xing, L., & Harrison, M. (2023). Europe PMC in 2023, *Nucleic Acids Research*, Volume 52, Issue D1, Pages D1668–D1676. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad1085>
- Rubin, M. (2022). The costs of HARKing. *British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, 73 (2), 535–560. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjps/axz050>
- Rushforth, A. (2025). Beyond impact factors? Lessons from the Dutch attempt to transform academic research assessment. *Research Evaluation*, 34, rvaf035. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvaf035>
- Scheel, A. M., Schijen, M. R. M. J., & Lakens, D. (2021). An excess of positive results: Comparing the standard psychology literature with Registered Reports. *Advances in Methods and Practices in Psychological Science*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/25152459211007467>
- Shu, F., Liu, S., & Larivière, V. (2022). China’s Research Evaluation Reform: What are the Consequences for Global Science? *Minerva* 60, 329–347 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11024-022-09468-7>
- Spick, M., Onoja, A., Harrison, C., Stender, S., Byrne, J., & Geifam, N. (2026). Quantifying new threats to health and biomedical literature integrity from rapidly scaled publications and problematic research. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2026.112203>
- Stodden, V., McNutt, M., Bailey, D. H., Deelman, E., Gil, Y., Hanson, B., Heroux, M. A., Ioannidis, J. P. A., & Taufer, M. (2016). Enhancing reproducibility for computational methods. *Science*, 354(6317), 1240–1241. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27940837/>
- Teixeira da Silva J. A. (2021). Non-compliance with ethical rules caused by misuse of ORCID accounts: Implications for medical publications in the COVID-19 era. *Ethics, medicine, and public health*, 18, 100692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jemep.2021.100692>

- The Royal Society (2024). *Science in the age of AI: How artificial intelligence is changing the nature and method of scientific research*. The Royal Society.
<https://royalsociety.org/news-resources/projects/science-in-the-age-of-ai/>
- Walsh, E., Rooney, M., Appleby, L., & Wilkinson, G. (2000). Open peer review: A randomised controlled trial. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 176(1), 47–51.
<https://doi.org/10.1192/bjp.176.1.47>
- Zhao, K., Li, J., & Liang, H. (2026). Reconfiguring power: a field analysis of China's research evaluation reform. *High Educ*, 91, 1469–1486. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-025-01480-6>